

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN : 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**

SJIF Impact Factor: 7.187

Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

A Case Study

**CASE STUDY ON PRIMARY HEALTH CARE CENTRES IN
RURAL AREAS OF WASHIM DISTRICT****Aniket R. Bhutkar¹, Vaibhav P. Gote², Dr. Swati P. Deshmukh³,
Prem R. Gabhane⁴, Suraj R. Magar⁵**^{1,4,5} Student of Shradhha Institute of Pharmacy, Washim 444505² Department of Pharmacognosy, Shradhha Institute of Pharmacy, Washim 444505³ Department of Pharmacology, Shradhha Institute of Pharmacy, Washim 444505**Abstract:**

This case study looks at the role and efficacy of primary healthcare centres (PHCs) in meeting the healthcare requirements of rural populations in Washim District, Maharashtra, India. The study looks into several aspects of PHCs, including access to healthcare services, infrastructure, staffing, community engagement, and health outcomes. Data gathering methods included interviews, surveys, and observational assessments at different PHCs in rural Washim District.

The study adds important insights to the ongoing efforts to achieve equal healthcare access and improve the well-being of rural populations in Washim District.

Keywords : Primary, Healthcare, Centres, PHCs, Rural, Washim, District

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Please cite this article in press Aniket R. Bhutkar et al., *Case Study On Primary Health Care Centres In Rural Areas Of Washim District*, Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2024; 11 (07).

INTRODUCTION:

A rural community is a town, a small settlement, or precinct that has a population of 2500 or less. These communities are often engaged in production industries such as farming, forestry, mining or fishing. Rural citizens have limited choice in their dwelling settings, lack of privacy from encroachment, and often live surrounded by land used for agricultural or resource production. This type of environment presents a unique occupational setting and health risk. Globalization has connected rural areas to urban communities and international society, thereby impacting the health of rural communities. Rural areas are marked by higher incidences of chronic illness with limited access to primary health care (PHC) services. High rates of disease, injury and limited access to health care are major contributors to higher individual and public health care costs. Improvements in rural health are essential to reducing health disparities between rural and urban communities. Rural communities often struggle in recruiting and maintaining generalist physicians and professionals in primary health care fields due to professional isolation and a lack of resources.

• **Background of Washim District :**

This Case Study is conducted to understand the primary health scenario of Washim district. For the purpose of primary health, it was necessary to take one district as a unit for study. So, Washim district was found to be most suitable for our purpose. One of the reasons for choosing Washim district is that the senior author is a member of various committees in the district and has quite knowledge of the district's rural area. Many NGOs are also working in the health sector for many years, and their experiences may reflect the impact of health services on health indicators of the district Washim. The Washim district came into existence on 1st July 1998; it was earlier a part of the district of Akola. The factors affecting the health of the district are that it is drought-prone. Most of the rainfall occurs during June to September. The climate is characterized by high temperatures, moderate relative humidity, and moderate to heavy rainfall. The district has a mixed pattern of agriculture. The available information regarding data on various health services and health indicators, experiences about prevalent health problems, and effectiveness of health services was considerable. The data was collected from various sources which are reported in subsequent lines. The Washim district has 6 blocks. The district has 1 medical college which is located in the government headquarters of the district, 1 civil hospital, 1 reveling hospital, 5 PHCs at Manora, Washim, Karanja, Malegaon, Risod.

• **Importance of Primary Healthcare Centres in Rural Areas :**

Primary health care (PHC) plays a crucial role in promoting health, preventing diseases, and ensuring equitable access to healthcare services. Here are some key reasons highlighting the importance of primary health care :

- 1. Gateway to Healthcare Services :** Primary health care serves as the first point of contact between individuals and the healthcare system. It addresses a majority of personal health needs throughout an individual's life, from prevention and treatment of common diseases to management of chronic conditions.
- 2. Preventive Care :** PHC emphasizes preventive measures such as vaccinations, screenings, and health education to promote healthy behaviours and reduce the risk of illnesses. By focusing on prevention, PHC can mitigate the burden of disease and lower healthcare costs.
- 3. Reducing Health Inequalities :** PHC strives for universal health coverage and equitable access to essential health services. It addresses disparities in healthcare access and outcomes, particularly for underserved populations in rural and remote areas.
- 4. Cost-Effectiveness:** Investing in primary health care is cost-effective in the long run. It helps prevent more expensive treatments by managing conditions early and reducing hospitalizations and emergency visits.
- 5. Coordination of Care :** PHC serves as a coordinator of care across different levels of the healthcare system. It ensures continuity of care and facilitates referrals to specialized services when needed.
- 6. Support for Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) :** PHC aligns with global health agendas, including the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). It contributes to achieving targets related to health, poverty reduction, and well-being.

• **Objective of Study :**

The objective of this case study is to assess the functioning, effectiveness, and challenges of Primary Healthcare Centers (PHCs) in rural areas of Washim district, Maharashtra, India, with a focus on improving healthcare access and outcomes for the local population. The study aims to achieve the following objectives :

- 1. Evaluate Healthcare Services**
- 2. Assess Infrastructure and Resources**
- 3. Understand Patient Demographics and Utilization**
- 4. Identify Challenges and Barriers**

5. Assess Community Engagement and Health Awareness

6. Provide Recommendations for Improvement

METHODOLOGY:

- **Data Collection from Different PHCs in Rural Areas of Washim District :**

1. **Identify and Select PHCs :** Begin by identifying a representative sample of PHCs located in different rural areas across Washim District. Ensure diversity in terms of geographical locations and patient populations served.

2. **Develop a Questionnaire :** Design a structured questionnaire to gather relevant information about PHC services, infrastructure, challenges, and community engagement. The questionnaire should include both (quantitative) and (qualitative) questions.

3. **Questionnaire Content :**

Include the following sections in the questionnaire :

- a. General Information

- b. Healthcare Services

- c. Infrastructure and Resources

- d. Patient Demographics and Utilization

- e. Challenges and Barriers

- f. Community Engagement and Health Promotion

- g. Recommendations and Feedback

4. **Pre-testing the Questionnaire :** Conduct a pilot test of the questionnaire with a small sample of PHC staff to identify and address any issues with question clarity, comprehensibility, or relevance.

5. **Data Collection Process :** Visit each selected PHC and administer the questionnaire to healthcare providers, administrators, and other relevant staff members. Conduct face-to-face interviews or distribute self-administered surveys based on the preference and availability of participants.

- **To compile data from different Primary Healthcare Centers (PHCs) in rural areas of Washim District :**

1. **Identify PHCs for Data Collection :** Create a list of PHCs located in different villages across Washim District. Ensure representation from various geographic areas within the district.

2. **Engage with PHC Staff and Authorities :** Contact PHC administrators or healthcare providers to obtain permission and schedule data collection visits. Explain the purpose and objectives of the data compilation to gain cooperation and support from PHC staff.

3. **Conduct Data Collection Visits :** Visit each identified PHC to administer the questionnaire and collect data from healthcare providers and staff. Conduct face-to-face interviews or distribute surveys based on the availability and preferences of participants.

4. **Record Responses :** Record responses systematically using paper-based forms. Ensure accuracy and completeness of data collection during the visits.

5. **Organize and Collate Data :** Organize collected data into a structured format, grouping responses by questionnaire sections (e.g., healthcare services, infrastructure, challenges). Create a centralized database or spreadsheet to compile data from all PHCs.

- **To analyse the collected data from different PHC in rural areas of Washim District :**

1. **Data Compilation and Cleaning :** Gather data from each PHC including patient records, medical treatments, demographics, facility infrastructure, staff details, and operational metrics. Ensure data consistency and completeness by addressing any missing values, duplicates, or errors.

2. **Descriptive Analysis :** Summarize key metrics for each PHC including patient throughput, service utilization rates, and availability of essential medical supplies.

3. **Comparative Analysis :** Compare performance indicators across different PHCs to identify variations and trends. Use visualizations like bar charts, pie charts, or tables to present comparative data on patient outcomes, disease prevalence, and resource allocation

4. **Health Service Accessibility and Utilization :** Analyze geographic accessibility to PHCs based on population distribution and distance. Assess utilization patterns to understand which PHCs are serving larger catchment areas or facing higher patient loads.

5. **Quality of Care Assessment :** Assess quality of care indicators such as patient satisfaction surveys or adherence to clinical guidelines. Identify areas for improvement in service quality and patient experience.

6. **Community Engagement and Feedback :** Incorporate community feedback through surveys or focus groups to understand local perspectives on healthcare services. Use qualitative data to complement quantitative analysis and inform tailored interventions.

- **To draw meaningful conclusions from the results of data collected from different**

Primary Health Centers (PHCs) in rural areas of Washim District :

1. **Review and Understand Data** : Thoroughly review the data collected from each PHC, including demographic information, health indicators, services provided, and operational metrics.
2. **Identify Key Findings** : Identify significant trends or patterns across the PHCs. This could include variations in patient demographics, disease prevalence, service utilization rates, or resource allocation.
3. **Compare and Contrast** : Compare performance metrics between different PHCs to highlight disparities and similarities. Look for factors contributing to differences in healthcare outcomes or service delivery.
4. **Assess Health Outcomes** : Evaluate health outcomes such as mortality rates, disease burden, and patient satisfaction across PHCs. Determine which PHCs are performing well and which areas need improvement.
5. **Community Impact** : Consider the impact of healthcare services on the local community. Evaluate accessibility, affordability, and satisfaction levels among residents.
6. **Public Health Implications** : Assess the public health implications of the findings. Identify priority health issues affecting the rural population. Determine areas where targeted interventions or public health programs could make a significant difference.
7. **Documentation and Reporting** : Document the conclusions and recommendations in a clear and concise manner. Prepare a comprehensive report outlining the analysis process, key findings, and actionable insights for stakeholders and decision-makers

Profile of Washim District :-

Washim District is situated in the Vidarbha region of Maharashtra, India. It is bordered by Yavatmal District to the north, Akola District to the west, Hingoli District to the south, and Buldhana District to the east. The administrative headquarters of Washim District is the town of Washim.

- **Geographic and Demographic Overview** :
 1. **Area** : Approximately 5,150 sq.km.
 2. **Topography** : The district features a mix of flat plains and undulating terrain.
 3. **Climate** : Washim experiences a semi-arid climate with hot summers and moderate winters.
 4. **Population** : As per the latest census of 2011, the population of Washim District is around 1,197,160 with a majority residing in rural areas.

5. **Demographic Composition** : The district is predominantly rural, with agriculture being the primary occupation.

- **Health and Healthcare Infrastructure** :

1. **Healthcare Facilities** : Washim District has a network of primary health centers (PHCs), community health centers (CHCs), and a district hospital located in Washim town.
2. **Primary Healthcare Services** : PHCs play a crucial role in delivering basic healthcare services to the rural population, including maternal and child healthcare, immunizations, and treatment for common ailments.
3. **Health Indicators** : Common health issues in the district include malaria, tuberculosis, malnutrition, and maternal mortality.
4. **Infrastructure Challenges** : Limited healthcare infrastructure and workforce shortages pose challenges to effective healthcare delivery.

- **Overview of Primary Healthcare Centers (PHCs) in Washim District** :

1. **Number of PHCs** : Washim District has a 25 PHCs and 153 subcentres strategically located across its rural areas to ensure accessibility to healthcare services.
2. **Geographical Coverage** : PHCs are distributed to cover a wide geographic area, providing healthcare access to remote and underserved communities.

Primary Healthcare Centres (PHC's) :-

A Primary Health Care (PHC) center is a frontline healthcare facility that provides essential and accessible health services to individuals and communities, especially in rural and underserved areas. The aim and objectives of PHC centers are aligned with the principles of primary healthcare as outlined by the World Health Organization (WHO) in the Alma-Ata Declaration.

- **Aim** : The aim of PHC centers is to ensure : Equitable access to essential health services for all individuals and communities. Comprehensive care that addresses the majority of health needs throughout the life cycle. Health promotion and disease prevention strategies that empower individuals to take control of their health. Integration of health services with other sectors to address social determinants of health.
- **Objectives** :
 1. **Promotion of Health and Prevention of Diseases** : Educate individuals and communities about healthy lifestyles, preventive measures, and disease prevention strategies. Conduct health

promotion campaigns, vaccination drives, and screening programs.

2. **Early Diagnosis and Treatment of Common Ailments** : Provide basic diagnosis and treatment for common health conditions such as respiratory infections, diarrheal diseases, and minor injuries. Manage chronic illnesses like diabetes, hypertension, and asthma through regular monitoring and medication.
3. **Maternal and Child Health Services** : Offer antenatal care, postnatal care, family planning services, and immunizations to promote safe motherhood and child health. Ensure skilled attendance during childbirth and monitor child growth and development.
4. **Basic Emergency Care** : Provide emergency first aid and stabilization services for acute illnesses and injuries before referring patients to higher-level facilities.
5. **Continuity of Care and Referral Services** : Establish ongoing relationships between healthcare providers and patients to ensure continuity of care. Facilitate referrals to specialized healthcare facilities for advanced diagnosis and treatment when needed.
6. **Community Engagement and Participation** : Engage local communities in health planning, implementation, and evaluation of PHC services. Empower communities through health education, awareness programs, and involvement in health committees.
7. **Equitable Access and Universal Health Coverage** : Ensure geographical accessibility to healthcare services by locating PHC centers close to the population they serve. Aim to achieve universal health coverage by providing essential health services that are affordable and accessible to all, especially vulnerable populations.

• **Services Offered at PHC's :**

Primary Healthcare Centers (PHCs) in rural areas offer a range of essential healthcare services aimed at promoting health, preventing diseases, and addressing the healthcare needs of the local population. The specific services provided may vary based on the resources available and the healthcare priorities of the region. Here are common services offered at PHCs in rural areas :

1. **Basic Medical Consultation** : Diagnosis and treatment of common health problems such as fever, respiratory infections, diarrhea, skin conditions, and minor injuries.
2. **Maternal and Child Health Services** : Antenatal care (ANC) for pregnant women, including regular check-ups, monitoring of

maternal health, and provision of iron-folic acid supplements. Postnatal care for new mothers, including breastfeeding support, family planning counselling, and immunizations for newborns.

3. **Immunization Services** : Vaccination services for infants and children to protect against vaccine-preventable diseases such as polio, measles, tetanus, diphtheria, and hepatitis B.
4. **Family Planning and Reproductive Health** : Counselling and provision of contraceptives to promote family planning and reproductive health. Screening for reproductive tract infections (RTIs) and sexually transmitted infections (STIs).
5. **Chronic Disease Management** : Management of chronic conditions such as diabetes, hypertension, asthma, and epilepsy through regular follow-up visits, medication management, and lifestyle counselling.
6. **Emergency Care and First Aid** : Basic emergency care for injuries, accidents, and acute illnesses, including wound dressing, fracture stabilization, and initial management of emergencies before referral to higher-level facilities.
7. **Community Outreach and Health Camps** : Conducting health camps and outreach programs in villages to provide health services, screenings, and health education to underserved populations. Engaging with community leaders and local organizations to promote health awareness and participation in healthcare activities.
8. **Referral Services** : Facilitating referrals to higher-level healthcare facilities for specialized care, diagnostic tests, and advanced treatment when needed.

Overall, PHCs in rural areas play a crucial role in delivering comprehensive primary healthcare services that are accessible, affordable, and culturally appropriate to meet the healthcare needs of rural communities. The services offered at PHCs contribute significantly to improving health outcomes, reducing morbidity and mortality, and promoting overall well-being in rural populations.

• **Staffing and Human Resources :**

Staffing and human resources in Primary Healthcare Centers (PHCs) in rural areas are essential for delivering quality healthcare services to the local population. The composition of staff and human resources at PHCs can vary depending on factors such as the size of the facility, the scope of services offered, and the specific healthcare needs of the community. Here are common staffing and human resources components found in PHCs in rural areas:

1. Medical Officer (Doctor) :

- a. Role : Provides clinical care, diagnosis, treatment, and management of patients.
- b. Qualifications : MBBS (Bachelor of Medicine, Bachelor of Surgery) or equivalent medical degree.
- c. Responsibilities : Oversees medical services, coordinates patient care, and provides guidance to other staff.

2. Nurses :

- a. Role : Assist with patient care, medication administration, wound dressing, immunizations, and health education.
- b. Qualifications : Diploma in Nursing (GNM – General Nursing and Midwifery) or B.Sc. Nursing.
- c. Responsibilities : Conducts routine assessments, assists in deliveries, and supports healthcare delivery.

3. Pharmacists :

- a. Role : Dispenses medications, provides drug information, and manages pharmacy operations.
- b. Qualifications : Diploma in Pharmacy (D.Pharm) or Bachelor of Pharmacy (B.Pharm).
- c. Responsibilities : Maintains drug inventory, ensures safe medication practices, and educates patients on medication use.

4. Laboratory Technicians :

- a. Role : Performs diagnostic tests, collects and analyzes specimens, and maintains laboratory equipment.
- b. Qualifications : Diploma or Bachelor's degree in Medical Laboratory Technology (DMLT or BMLT).
- c. Responsibilities : Conducts tests like blood sugar, hemoglobin, malaria smear, and urine analysis.

5. Auxiliary Nurse Midwives (ANMs) :

- a. Role : Assists in maternal and child health services, immunizations, and family planning activities.

- b. Qualifications : Diploma in Auxiliary Nurse Midwifery (ANM) or equivalent.
- c. Responsibilities : Conducts antenatal visits, assists in deliveries, and provides postnatal care.

6. Community Health Workers (ASHAs – Accredited Social Health Activists) :

- a. Role : Acts as a link between the community and healthcare services, conducts health awareness campaigns, and supports health programs.
- b. Qualifications : Training provided by government health agencies.
- c. Responsibilities : Conducts home visits, facilitates referrals, and promotes health-seeking behaviors.

7. Support Staff :

1. Role : Includes administrative staff, cleaners, and security personnel.
2. Responsibilities : Assists in facility management, maintenance, and support services.

8. Additional Resources and Support :

- a. Telemedicine Services : Remote consultation with specialists for complex cases.
- b. Training and Capacity Building : Continuous training programs for staff to enhance skills and knowledge.
- c. Collaboration with NGOs and Volunteers : Engaging with non-governmental organizations (NGOs) and community volunteers to support healthcare initiatives.

Effective staffing and human resource management are crucial for optimizing healthcare delivery and ensuring the availability of essential services at PHCs in rural areas. Governments and health organizations focus on recruiting and retaining skilled healthcare professionals, providing training opportunities, and implementing supportive policies to strengthen primary healthcare services in rural communities.

Questionnaire :**Case Study On Primary Healthcare Centres In Rural Areas Of Washim District**

Sr. No.	Question	Yes	No	Don't Know
1	The infrastructure of your PHC building is adequate to handle the patients in your area?			
2	Do you have sufficient number of physicians in your PHC?			
3	Do you have all the facilities available as per NRHM guidelines?			
4	Do you have separate rooms for each department?			
5	The number of employees required above PHC level are available?			
6	Do you have individual employees for each department?			
7	Is cleanliness maintain in your PHC?			
8	Do you have all the required equipment above PHC level?			
9	Are the required number of beds as per NRHM guidelines available in your PHC?			
10	Ambulance facility available in your PHC?			
11	Are the patients this is properly diagnosed by the facilities in PHC?			
12	You go to the remote areas under your PHC for health camps conducted by the government?			
13	Do you conduct disease awareness programme's of government?			
14	Is there a prevalence of communicable diseases in your area?			
15	Does the PHC have a fire safety system for emergencies?			
16	Did you find the information given by the staff at PHC is correct?			
17	Whether you find the cleanliness there good or not?			
18	Did you find the behaviour of the staff in PHC good?			
19	Are the patients satisfied with the treatment there?			
20	Are all the services in PHC running smoothly?			

• Data Sheet :

Sr. No.	Questions	PHC No.									
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
		Marks									
1	The infrastructure of your PHC building is adequate to handle the patients in your area?	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
2	Do you have sufficient number of physicians in your PHC?	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
3	Do you have all the facilities available as per NRHM guidelines?	5	5	0	5	5	5	5	5	0	5
4	Do you have separate rooms for each department?	5	5	0	5	5	5	5	5	0	5
5	The number of employees required above PHC level are available?	5	0	0	5	0	0	0	5	0	5
6	Do you have individual employees for each department?	5	0	0	0	5	0	0	5	0	5
7	Is cleanliness maintain in your PHC?	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
8	Do you have all the required equipment above PHC level?	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
9	Are the required number of beds as per NRHM guidelines available in your PHC?	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
10	Ambulance facility available in your PHC?	5	5	0	5	0	5	0	5	0	0
11	Are the patients this is properly diagnosed by the facilities in PHC?	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
12	You go to the remote areas under your PHC for health camps conducted by the government?	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
13	Do you conduct disease awareness programme's of government?	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
14	Is there a prevalence of communicable diseases in your area?	0	5	0	5	5	5	5	0	0	5
15	Does the PHC have a fire safety system for emergencies?	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
16	Did you find the information given by the staff at PHC is correct?	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
17	Whether you find the cleanliness there good or not?	5	5	5	0	0	0	0	0	5	0
18	Did you find the behaviour of the staff in PHC good?	5	5	5	0	5	0	5	5	5	5
19	Are the patients satisfied with the treatment there?	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
20	Are all the services in PHC running smoothly?	5	5	5	0	5	5	5	5	5	5
Total		95	90	70	80	85	80	80	90	70	90

Marking Scale : Yes = 5 M, No = 0.

Grading Chart :

0 – 25	Below Average
26 – 50	Average
51 – 75	Good
76 – 100	Better

CONCLUSION:

By this data collection from the survey it conclude that the case study on primary healthcare centers (PHCs) in rural areas of Washim District reveals both

strengths and areas for improvement in the healthcare delivery system for the rural population. The following are significant findings and conclusions from the study:

1. **Improved Access to Healthcare :** The establishment of PHCs has significantly enhanced access to essential healthcare services for rural communities in Washim District. By bringing healthcare closer to the population, PHCs have helped reduce barriers related to distance and transportation.
2. **Essential Health Services :** PHCs play a vital role in providing a range of essential health services including maternal and child healthcare, immunizations, treatment of common illnesses, and health education. These services are crucial for improving health outcomes and reducing morbidity and mortality rates.
3. **Community Engagement and Awareness :** Efforts to promote community engagement and raise awareness about preventive healthcare practices have shown positive outcomes. Community members are increasingly participating in health education programs and adopting healthier behaviours.
4. **Healthcare Infrastructure :** There have been positive strides in upgrading healthcare infrastructure at PHCs, including the availability of basic medical equipment, essential medicines, and improved facilities. This contributes to the overall quality of care provided to rural residents.
5. **Healthcare Staffing and Training :** While challenges with staffing persist, initiatives aimed at recruiting and training healthcare professionals have yielded promising results. Capacity-building programs enhance the skills of existing staff and attract new talent to serve in rural areas.
6. **Government Support and Initiatives :** The support of government schemes and initiatives such as the National Rural Health Mission (NRHM) has played a pivotal role in strengthening primary healthcare services in Washim District. Increased funding and policy attention are crucial for the development and sustainability of PHCs.
7. **Challenges and Opportunities for Improvement :** Despite progress, challenges remain, including staffing shortages, limited resources, and infrastructure gaps. Addressing these challenges requires continuous

investment, strategic planning, and community involvement to further strengthen PHCs.

In conclusion, the case study emphasises the good impact of primary healthcare centres in rural Washim District while also indicating areas for future improvement. Continued investment, policy support, and new approaches are required to guarantee fair access to quality healthcare services and to meet the changing health requirements of the rural population. By tackling these problems and building on previous triumphs, Washim District's healthcare system may continue to make considerable progress towards improving health outcomes and the well-being of its rural residents.

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